

DECISION-MAKING IN CHOOSING TOURISM MANAGEMENT AT DE LA SALLE UNIVERSITY - DASMARIÑAS AMIDST PANDEMIC

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Abstract: The COVID-19 pandemic has impacted people around the world in different ways. One of the major changes within the tourism industry is the use of online learning. The purpose of this study was to evaluate disparities in gender and year in school, such as those between freshmen and sophomores, in terms of participants' Expectations, Motivations, and Behaviors. The research study aims to determine the factors determining first-year students' decision-making in choosing Tourism Management at DLSU-Dasmariñas. The study was a pilot study consisting of twenty HTM students. The most current research on the reasons why Asian students choose to major in HTM was used as a guide for determining the motivation statements that would be included in the survey instrument. The analysis of the data for this study was carried out in three stages. [1] information on the respondents was obtained from the findings of descriptive statistics (means and frequency). [2] the data that were gathered were subjected to a factor analysis in order to determine the fundamental aspects of HTM research expectations, motivations, and behaviors. [3] Only factors that had an eigenvalue of more than one were considered valid, and only items that had factor loadings and commonalities greater than 0.4 were included in the final factor structure. The results of the study show that there is no significant difference in the decision of freshmen students for choosing tourism management in a school with a high tourism enrollment rate of 246 from the previous term. It is also hypothesized that the demographic profile of the respondents is a significant factor that determines the decision. In addition, the results of this exploratory study will aid in identifying the topic areas within HTM in which Filipino students prefer to concentrate in their studies of the subject. The findings of this research study will provide awareness, understanding, and an opportunity to recognize.

Keywords: COVID-19, Pandemic, Decision-making, tourism, expectations, motivations, behaviors, online learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Tourism is famous to have surprisingly wonderful significance in the business-related facet of a country, as it stresses the lack of laborers in manufacturing so that it can develop skillful staff. Larger parts of the industry within the world have been extremely hit by COVID-19 and one of them is the Tourism industry, where the economy is generally subordinate. A portion of the industry that was hit to a great extent by the widespread is the tourism instruction that speaks to an imperative

part in molding the understudies to be industry-ready and proficient. It is said that 32 nations around the world have school shutdowns driving 91% of understudies around the world- around 1.6 billion children were influenced and are not able to proceed with instruction. Which afterward drove the schools to offer online learning for their understudies to proceed with education.

People around the world have been affected in different ways by the COVID-19 pandemic. Several things were changed in the Philippines and around the world as a result of this outbreak. As a result, the outbreak has caused disruption to tourism and other related sectors nationally and globally (Jamal and Budke, 2020). Due to the unpredictability of the conditions, the virus had an unanticipated impact on the tourism and hotel industries not just in the Philippines, but globally. The world economy was hindered as a result of the epidemic (Haleem et al., 2020). According to Skare et al. (2021), the COVID-19 situation puts 75 million people at risk at work, with one hundred employees losing their employment.

One of the major changes within the tourism industry is the use of online learning. Online learning is extraordinary to ensure useful education by giving the opportunity to understudies to interconnect with a framework that suits their information and behavior. By providing students with the opportunity to connect with a platform that is tailored to their knowledge and behavior, online education is a fantastic way to guarantee effective instruction. It is significant since that takes into account the individual traits required of a learner in relation to the course resources. Nevertheless, it is additionally necessary to examine the learners' understanding.

Since the early 1990s, the number of universities in the Philippines that offer degrees in hospitality and tourism management (hence referred to as HTM) has increased dramatically. The scope of hospitality and tourism has expanded thanks to the introduction of new topics including the administration of conventions and exhibitions, special events, cruises, airlines, theme parks, private clubs, and casinos. In addition to the conventional HTM topic areas, such as hotels and resorts, restaurants, institution administration, leisure studies, and tourism, students now have several possibilities from which to select. During the past twenty years, there has been a more than fourfold increase in the number of postsecondary schools that offer programs in hospitality and tourism (Dangi et al., 2022).

According to the report that was published by the International Council on Hotel, Restaurant, and Institutional Education (Kim et al., 2020), in the year 2020, there were 251 educational institutions in the United States that offered HTM-related degrees, certificates, or diplomas to a total of almost 57 thousand students. When compared to the statistics from 1991, these results reveal a mean growth of 43% in the number of educational institutions and 48% in the number of students over the course of a period of 13 years. Because of the rapid expansion of HTM programs, there is now an intense level of rivalry among those programs, with each seeking to attract a higher quality student body as well as a greater number of students. Investigations have been conducted on a variety of different topics, one of which is the topic of study motives. These investigations have sought to discover what inspires students to major in hospitality and tourism management (Kim et al., 2020). However, there have only been a few studies done to investigate the reasons why students in the Philippines chose HTM as their major.

As a result, the primary objective of this research was to investigate the views held by students concerning the factors that influence their decision to major in HTM. In particular, the purpose of this study was to evaluate disparities in gender and year in school, such as those between freshmen and sophomores, in terms of participants' expectations, motivations, and behaviors. In addition, the survey evaluated which area of HTM students wanted to focus their academic pursuits on. It is possible that the findings of this exploratory study will assist HTM institutions in revising and improving their curriculum in response to the perspectives of their students.

The purpose of this study was to bring tourism students' awareness of how they can learn during this unexpected pandemic, as there have been very few studies of this kind conducted in tourist academia. We conducted this study to determine what motivates tourism students to continue their studies after DLSU-Dasmariñas' tourism enrollment declined from 280 to 246 from the previous term.

This study assessed and determined the factors determining first-year students' decision-making in choosing tourism management at De La Salle University - Dasmariñas amidst the pandemic. Prior to this, it would only focus on the effect of the variables on the decision of freshmen and second-year students for choosing Tourism Management and to find out any significant difference in the decision-making of the respondents for choosing Tourism Management in DLSU-D amidst the pandemic.

The study will only be done at De La Salle University - Dasmariñas from which the respondents will be students of Tourism Management. Hence limitations such as weaknesses of this study pertain to the accuracy of the respondent's perception and the rate of inadequacy as their suggestions and recommendations shall base on their personal experience and may not be accurately correct.

The research study aims to determine the factors determining first-year students' decision-making in choosing tourism management at De La Salle University - Dasmariñas amidst the pandemic. Specifically, the study aims to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:

1.1 Age

1.2 Gender

1.3 Year

2. What is the effect of the variables on the decision of freshmen students for choosing Tourism Management in DLSU-D amidst the pandemic in terms of:

2.1. Expectation

2.2. Motivation

2.3. Behavior

3. What is the effect of the variables on the decision of second-year students for choosing Tourism Management in DLSU-D amidst the pandemic in terms of:

3.1. Expectation

3.2. Motivation

3.3. Behavior

4. Is there any significant difference in the decision-making of the respondents for choosing Tourism Management in DLSU-D amidst the pandemic and their demographic profile when grouped accordingly?

5. Based on the study results, what suggestions and recommendations can be proposed to address the decision-making of the respondents for choosing Tourism Management in DLSU-D amidst the pandemic?

It is hypothesized that there is no significant difference in the decision-making of the respondents for choosing Tourism Management in DLSU-D amidst the pandemic and their demographic profile when grouped accordingly. The result of the study will aid in determining the factors that determine the first-year student's decision-making in choosing tourism management at De La Salle University - Dasmariñas amidst the pandemic. The following will benefit the following:

Tourism Management Students. This research will provide information that will help them learn the skills they need to succeed in their chosen field, helping them build a better future. Right course selection can help students fit into their interests and learn more about a field they're genuinely interested in studying.

Faculty of Tourism Management. When students make a decision, they're more likely to own it. Less blame can be put on the teacher if students don't like what they're learning. Making the decision about what to learn encourages students to accept more of the responsibility for learning.

Future Researchers. The research will provide accurate information to future researchers that will choose a study similar to ours. Future researchers who want to pursue the same topic for further development and improvement will benefit from the findings of this study. Moreover, it provides knowledge and easy access to gathering lessons for students. They can also include it in their review of the literature.

Readers. This study will provide awareness, understanding, and an opportunity to recognize the needs not only of the students but also the importance of students' decision-making but also to various other schools and students with similar findings and results as our research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL/THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Evaluations of one's situation, both cognitive and affective, frequently serve as the basis for one's level of happiness. The theoretical underpinning of this study is based on the findings of a number of other studies, all of which agree that cognitive beliefs and affective/emotional reactions play an important part in the formation of satisfaction (Lane & Smith, 2021).

According to the findings of these researchers, the amount of satisfaction may be calculated using evaluative judgments that are based on both cognitive and emotive reactions. In particular, Topcuoglu et al. (2022) discovered that guests' cognitive and affective aspects of appraisal for a green hotel product have a significant interrelation and that such a relationship triggers satisfaction and behavioral intentions. In addition, the researchers found that guests' cognitive and affective aspects of appraisal for a green hotel product were positively correlated with each other. More recently, Winter et al. (2020) conducted an analysis of the post-purchase behaviors of airline consumers.

Through this research, they were able to experimentally establish that cognitive and emotional assessments of airline services are key drivers of passenger happiness. Their findings also suggested that although both cognitive and emotive elements contribute directly to a person's level of satisfaction, the cognitive assessment also has an indirect impact on a person's level of satisfaction through the medium of affective evaluation. This high link between cognitive and emotive components and the mediating influence was in keeping with Wang et al. (2020)'s assessment of the function of cognitive and affective evaluations in the context of tourism. The cognitive evaluation that individuals provide of a product or service triggers the emotional responses that are important to its performance, which in turn affects the amount of satisfaction that they experience (Hsu, 2022). This finding is consistent with Ma et al. (2022)'s theory, which proposes that cognitive and emotive evaluations of a product or service and the features of that product or service have a significant link in the process of creating pleasure. It is therefore hypothesized that the cognitive assessment of a course by students is positively connected to their affective appraisal of a course and that student satisfaction with the course is a positive function of both variables.

3. METHODOLOGY

The researchers were able to make a number of preliminary conclusions regarding the survey instrument that would be used after doing a review of the existing body of research on HTM study motives. The most current research on the reasons why Asian students choose to major in HTM (Sidhu & Ishikawa, 2022) was used as a guide for determining the motivation statements that would be included in the survey instrument. In order to assist in the process of determining the scope of the initial questionnaire, a pilot study consisting of twenty HTM students was carried out. The initial questionnaire was modified

as a direct result of the pilot research, as well as additional consultation with both professional colleagues and student representatives. This was done in order to make room for some degree of cultural variation across the Philippines. After the results of the pilot research were analyzed, some motivating statements that were deemed to be confusing or ambiguous were removed, bringing the total number of motivational statements down from 24 in the initial survey instrument to 20. The final survey consisted of 20 motivating statements, each of which was scored on a Likert scale from 1 to 4, with 1 indicating that the respondent strongly disagreed with the statement and 4 indicating that they strongly agreed with the statement. In addition, the questionnaire included questions that asked respondents for demographic information, such as their age, gender, and the year in which they were enrolled in school. This was done in order to investigate the extent to which the perspectives of students regarding HTM study vary depending on demographic factors.

At the present time, the total number of undergraduate students majoring in HTM who are registered at DLSU is [246]. These institutions provided their consent to take part in this study, and as a result, approval from the Institutional Review Boards (IRBs) of each of the three institutions that took part was acquired prior to the collection of data.

During the school year 2022-2023, questionnaires were sent out to participants. In order to eliminate any possibility of bias in the results, the survey was given out at the same time to each and every student. This research is concentrating on one of the various HTM classes that are available at each university; specifically, tourism management.

The analysis of the data for this study was carried out in three stages. In the first place, information on the respondents was obtained from the findings of descriptive statistics (means and frequency). In the second step of the process, the data that were gathered were subjected to a factor analysis in order to determine the fundamental aspects of HTM research expectations, motivations, and behaviors. Only factors that had an eigenvalue of more than one were considered valid, and only items that had factor loadings and commonalities greater than 0.4 were included in the final factor structure. This was done in accordance with the recommendation made by Shrestha (2021).

According to Armstrong (2019), the Pearson correlation coefficient, which is also known as the product-moment correlation coefficient, is represented by the letter r in a sample. On the other hand, it is represented by the letter R in the population from which the sample was collected. A representative sample was taken from the population, and the coefficient of correlation calculated by Pearson is denoted by the letter r . On a scale that does not have any units associated with it, the value of the coefficient can range anywhere from -1 all the way up to +1 at any given time. If the sign of the correlation coefficient was negative, then there would have been a negative correlation, which would have shown that those participant demographics were connected, and vice versa. This will be utilized to measure the statistical significance of expectation, motivation, and behavior.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter provides an analysis and interpretation of the data that was collected via the use of statistical measures. Results are arranged in a manner that is consistent with the sequence in which the issues have been stated, and they are expounded upon in an alternative presentation of the metaphorical results that have been gained from the many tests that have been carried out.

Table 1. Age of the Participants

		AGE			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18	10	20.0	20.0	20.0
	19	23	46.0	46.0	66.0
	20	17	34.0	34.0	100.0
Total		50	100.0	100.0	

Table 1 assessed the age of the participants. Out of 50 participants, 10 (20 percent) were 18 years old, 23 (46 percent) were 19 years old, and 17 (34 percent) were 20 years old. This shows that the majority of participants lie in the age of 19 years old.

Table 2. Gender of the Participants

		GENDER			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	27	54.0	54.0	54.0
	LGBTQIA+	1	2.0	2.0	56.0
	Male	22	44.0	44.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 tallied the gender of the participants. Out of 50 participants, 27 (54 percent) were female, 22 (44 percent) were male, and 1 participant (2 percent) identifies themselves as LGBTQIA+. This shows that the pool of participants is diverse, with a good mix of males and females, while the marginalized community is being represented as well.

Table 3. Year of the Participants

		YEAR			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Freshmen	22	44.0	44.0	44.0
	Sophomore	28	56.0	56.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Table 3 counted the number of participants who participated in the study, in terms of their year levels. Out of 50 participants, 22 (44 percent) identified themselves as freshmen, while 28 (56 percent) identified themselves as sophomores. This shows that the majority of the participants are sophomores, however, almost half of the participants were freshmen.

Expectations

Table 4. Expectations of the Participants

Statements	Year Level	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Verbal Conclusion
<i>Category of Conclusions</i>		<i>Disagree</i>		<i>Agree</i>		
I believe that there is a variety of job opportunities.	Freshmen	0	2	15	5	Agree
	Sophomore	1	2	13	12	Agree
After I graduate, I can have many opportunities to travel and work in foreign countries.	Freshmen	1	1	10	10	Agree
	Sophomore	0	2	14	12	Agree
I believe that the percentage of employment is high after graduation.	Freshmen	0	0	9	13	Agree
	Sophomore	0	1	15	12	Agree
I believe that this field has growth potential.	Freshmen	0	1	10	11	Agree
	Sophomore	1	2	11	14	Agree

Scenes or pictures of the hospitality industry appearing in movies or TV look attractive.	Freshmen	2	1	11	8	Agree
	Sophomore	0	2	12	14	Agree
Compared to other fields, this field provides more opportunities for promotion.	Freshmen	0	0	8	14	Agree
	Sophomore	0	0	16	12	Agree

In Table 4, we take a look at what the participants had in mind. Participants who are in their first and second years of college believe that there is a wide range of employment opportunities, that there are many opportunities to travel and work in foreign countries, that the percentage of employment is high after graduation, that this field has growth potential, that scenes or pictures of the hospitality industry that appear in movies or on television look appealing, and that this field provides more opportunities for promotion when compared to other fields. This illustrates that the participants, when assessed both collectively and individually according to year, have normally high expectations.

Motivation

Table 5. Motivation of the Participants

Statements	Year Level	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Verbal Conclusion
<i>Category of Conclusions</i>		<i>Disagree</i>		<i>Agree</i>		
I would like to study more in this field.	Freshmen	0	0	14	8	Agree
	Sophomore	0	1	10	17	Agree
I feel that a career in the hospitality and tourism industry will enable me to meet my personal goals.	Freshmen	1	1	11	9	Agree
	Sophomore	1	3	14	10	Agree
I have more interest in this field compared to others.	Freshmen	1	1	13	7	Agree
	Sophomore	0	2	13	13	Agree
I like to serve others.	Freshmen	0	1	11	10	Agree
	Sophomore	1	2	20	5	Agree
Working in this field apparently looks good.	Freshmen	1	2	8	11	Agree
	Sophomore	4	1	16	7	Agree
Recommended by others (e.g., parents, friends, teachers).	Freshmen	2	3	8	9	Agree
	Sophomore	2	1	13	12	Agree

The participants' levels of motivation are broken down in Table 5. They feel that a career in the hospitality and tourism industry will enable them to meet their personal goals, that they have more interest in this field compared to others, that they like to serve others, that they believe that working in this field apparently looks good and that their parents, friends, and teachers recommended that they take this course. Freshmen and sophomores are in agreement that they would like to

study more in this field, that they feel that a career in the hospitality and tourism industry will enable them to meet their personal goals and that they feel this demonstrates that the participants have a significant amount of enthusiasm for the course on tourist management.

Behavior

Table 6. Behavior of the Participants

Statements	Year Level	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Verbal Conclusion
<i>Category of Conclusions</i>		<i>Disagree</i>		<i>Agree</i>		
My scores on entrance exams qualified me for this major.	Freshmen	2	2	9	9	Agree
	Sophomore	4	3	11	10	Agree
Compared to other fields, it is easy to study this field.	Freshmen	0	1	7	14	Agree
	Sophomore	1	3	13	11	Agree
I believe that this field is practical rather than theoretical.	Freshmen	4	0	8	10	Agree
	Sophomore	0	1	15	12	Agree
I feel that my skills match the demands & requirements of the hospitality and tourism industry.	Freshmen	0	1	6	15	Agree
	Sophomore	2	2	8	16	Agree
I believe I do have what it takes to pass this course.	Freshmen	0	0	10	12	Agree
	Sophomore	2	2	13	11	Agree

As can be seen in Table 6, the participants' behaviors during this training were evaluated and analyzed. Students in their first and second years of college are in agreement regarding the following points: their scores on the entrance exams qualified them for this major; when compared to other fields, it is easy to study this field; they believe that this field is more practical than theoretical; they believe that their skills match the demands and requirements of the hospitality and tourism industry; and they believe that they do what it takes to pass the course. This demonstrates that the participants are highly anticipatory and highly driven towards the tourist management course; yet, their conduct lends credence to the assumption that they are going to graduate in this course, and that they will enjoy the entirety of the time that they are doing it.

Correlations

Table 7. Correlations

		E_Mean	M_Mean	B_Mean	AGE	GENDER	YEAR
E_Mean	Pearson Correlation	1	-.398	.556	.233	.213	.458
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.434	.252	.656	.152	.361
	N	6	6	6	6	6	6
M_Mean	Pearson Correlation	-.398	1	-.717	-.255	-.425	-.551
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.434		.108	.626	.223	.257
	N	6	6	6	6	6	6
B_Mean	Pearson Correlation	.556	-.717	1	-.193	.054	.173
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.252	.108		.715	.087	.743
	N	6	6	6	6	6	6
AGE	Pearson Correlation	.233	-.255	-.193	1	-.107	.731**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.656	.626	.715		.459	.000
	N	6	6	6	50	50	50
GENDER	Pearson Correlation				-.107	1	-.321*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.459		.023
	N	6	6	6	50	50	50
YEAR	Pearson Correlation	.458	-.551	.173	.731**	-.321*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.361	.257	.743	.000	.023	
	N	6	6	6	50	50	50

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

As can be seen in Table 7, the data of the participants' demographics were compared against their expectations, motivation, and conduct. There is not a significant difference found between age ($r = 0.233$, $p = 0.656$), gender ($r = 0.213$, $p = 0.152$), or year ($r = 0.458$, $p = 0.361$) in terms of one's level of anticipation. There is not a significant age difference for motivation ($r = -0.255$, $p = 0.626$), gender difference for motivation ($r = -0.425$, $p = 0.223$), or year difference for motivation ($r = -0.551$, $p = 0.257$). There is no discernible variation in behavior based on age ($r = -0.193$, $p = 0.715$), gender ($r = 0.054$, $p = 0.087$), or year ($r = 0.173$, $p = 0.743$). The p-values of the variables demonstrate that, despite the fact that there are varying degrees of positive and negative correlations, such as the idea that as one's age increases, so do one's expectations and level of motivation, these correlations are, for the most part, negligible.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The pool of participants is broad, with a decent mix of boys and girls, while the marginalized population is represented as well. The demographics suggest that the majority of participants are sophomores, while over half of the participants were first-year students.

Participants who are in their first and second years of college believe that the hospitality industry offers a wide variety of employment opportunities, that there are many opportunities to travel and work in foreign countries, that the percentage of employment is high after graduation, that this field has growth potential, that scenes or pictures of the hospitality industry that appear in movies or on television look appealing, and that this field provides more opportunities for promotion when compared to other fields. This demonstrates that the participants, when evaluated collectively and individually according to year, often have high aspirations for themselves.

Both of these years believe that a job in the hospitality and tourism industry will enable them to meet their personal goals, that they have a greater interest in this field compared to others, that they enjoy serving other people, that they believe that working in this field apparently looks good and that their parents, friends, and teachers recommended that they take this course. Both of these years also believe that a career in the hospitality and tourism industry will enable them to meet their personal goals. They believe that a career in the hospitality and tourism industry will enable them to meet their personal goals and this demonstrates that the participants have a significant amount of enthusiasm for the course on tourist management. Both first-year students and second-year students are in agreement that they would like to study more in this field.

The following is a list of topics on which students in their freshman and sophomore years of college unanimously agree: They believe that their abilities match the demands and requirements of the hospitality and tourism industry, that they do what it takes to pass the course, and that their scores on the entrance exams qualified them for this major; when compared to other fields, it is easy to study this field; they believe that this field is more practical than theoretical; they believe that this field is more practical than theoretical; they believe that this field is more practical than theoretical; they believe that this field is more practical than theoretical; they believe that this field is more practical than theoretical; they However, the participants' behavior lends credence to the assumption that they are going to graduate in this course, and that they will enjoy the entirety of the time that they are doing it. This demonstrates that the participants are highly anticipatory and highly driven towards the tourist management course.

The p-values of the variables show that, despite the fact that there are varying degrees of positive and negative correlations, such as the concept that as one gets older, their expectations and level of motivation also increase, these correlations are, for the most part, insignificant. This is the case despite the fact that there are varying degrees of positive and negative correlations.

It's possible that researchers, educational institutions, and other stakeholders may be interested in learning more about the motives behind HTM studies. However, to the best of our knowledge, there has only been a modest amount of study carried out in this field. In particular, issues concerning the reasons that Filipino students choose to study HTM as well as their favorite study areas within HTM have been left unaddressed for a considerable amount of time. Therefore, the primary goal of this study was to address this research vacuum by outlining the reasons why college students in the Philippines choose to study HTM and by identifying the topic areas within HTM in which Filipino students prefer to concentrate in their studies of the subject.

Notable themes that were brought up by students included the opinion that the hospitality and tourism industry is interesting; possibly as a result of this interest, students would like to continue their education and/or professional development at home

or abroad; students enjoy providing service to other people; and students believe that their skills will be sufficient, upon graduation, to meet the demands and requirements of the hospitality and tourism industry.

The decision to direct resources toward developing subfields within hospitality and tourism in order to cater to the interests of students raises the question of what can be done to improve learning and pedagogy within these more contemporary subfields as they are presented in the classroom. Consultation with a center for teaching excellence may be of great assistance in the process of designing newer courses (as well as retrofitting traditional courses) to align with the learning styles of modern students, while also offering insights into innovative teaching methods. This may be of great benefit to those involved in the process. On the other hand, conventional parts of the curriculum (which students may exhibit less interest in) should be reexamined to see whether or not they still satisfy the needs of students and faculty alike, and they could be changed if those needs are not being met. The content of foundational HTM courses like lodging, tourism, and restaurant management, which are typically prerequisites for more specialized courses, could be augmented with information from emerging fields in the hospitality and tourism industries without cannibalizing the material covered in higher-level specialty or elective programs. It's also possible for beginner HTM classes to incorporate information hand-picked from a variety of new and developing topics. Before beginning the next phase of their educational program, this can make it easier for students to make decisions on the types of courses they want to take in more specialized fields of study. It would be good to get input from industry professionals in order to determine which components of present and developing hospitality education will improve employment prospects and help identify the skills that employers seek. Before making any course adjustments, it is important to get the thoughtful attention of all HTM stakeholders.

It is possible that doing an analysis of the prevalence of HTM in Philippine higher education will be beneficial for all parties involved in the HTM academic community, including institutions, students, and the industry. In the first place, it can assist the general public in better comprehending the present standing of the HTM field inside the Philippine higher education system. Second, the findings of this inquiry may have an impact on the ways in which HTM schools create their curricula as well as their recruitment practices. Third, the hospitality and tourism business may be able to profit from this research regarding HTM students for the purpose of hiring new employees and formulating new policies.

Although the findings of this study give new information, it is important to highlight that this study cannot claim to be typical of all HTM institutions or of all HTM students. This is despite the fact that the results of this study provide new information. Rather, the most important findings should be seen as an indicator of the ways in which students at other HTM schools can be persuaded to pick HTM as their major. This study offers a glimpse of student opinion; nevertheless, the true value of students' perspectives resides in their use in longitudinal research (Xu et al., 2022). In light of the fact that its primary function is to serve as a device for the production of individualized educational experiences for pupils, a method known as the longitudinal approach might be utilized in order to provide comparability and benchmark performance across various student groups and over the course of time.

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